

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D1.3

Federated discovery across registry services

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Lead Beneficiary:	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
WP Leader(s):	Lauren Fromont, Karen Cranston, and Jordi Rambla de Argila
Contributing Partner(s):	-
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Author of this Deliverable:	Lauren Fromont (CRG)
Contributors:	Gemma Milla (CRG)
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Approved by:	Thomas Keane
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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable tackles a main challenge of the CINECA project and federated analysis: Federated data discovery. To address it, it offers a Discovery portal that allows users to search for specific individuals or cohorts and get details about them. For demonstration purposes, this portal only includes synthetic, non sensitive data.

2. Project objectives

Federated data discovery has been identified as the primary challenge of the CINECA project since its inception. Indeed, perhaps the most fundamental barrier to enhanced reuse of human data and biomaterials is to provide standardised methods and portals for federated search and discovery of relevant human data. There are several axes of data discovery, e.g. disease status, data use, sample collection parameters, genotype, phenotype, and data type.

In response to this challenge, this deliverable has contributed to the following project objectives:

- a) Implementing discovery and querying services atop each resource, for querying based on genetic variants, phenotypes, and data access limitations.
- b) Developing a programmatically queryable catalogue of such services. Implementing federated querying over the services in the Catalog. Developing interactive portals for the discovery and examination of the distributed data.
- c) Building discovery services atop data models and APIs interoperable federated clinical and research analyses so that, for instance, a user can run uniform pipelines on distributed cohorts discovered through the tools developed here.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

A key obstacle to solving diseases is the difficulty of discovering relevant cohort datasets from different organisations and projects, to power applications in academic, clinical, pharmaceutical, and genomics research. With the amount of genomic data rapidly growing¹, the traditional approach of data aggregation in a single centralised site does not work. For example, patient phenotypes, especially in longitudinal studies, are dynamic measurements but often represented as static variables in centralised database models. A federated system capable of executing cross-dataset and cross-institution queries enables variables to be queried and updated at source.

¹ Navarro, F.C.P., Mohsen, H., Yan, C. *et al.* Genomics and data science: an application within an umbrella. *Genome Biol* 20, 109 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-019-1724-1>

The Global Alliance for Genomics & Health (GA4GH) is a standards-setting organisation for responsible genomics data sharing; several of the partners in WP1 are in leadership positions in the GA4GH as driver projects. One important group at the GA4GH is the Beacon API (ELIXIR Beacon driver project), co-championed by Jordi Rambla and coordinated by Lauren Fromont. This group has been working on Beacon version 2, a protocol that defines an open standard for federated discovery of genomic (and “phenoclinic”) data in biomedical research and clinical applications. This protocol was officially accepted as a GA4GH standard in 2022².

The Beacon v2 standard is the cornerstone of the work presented in this deliverable.

3.2 Description of Work

The Federated discovery portal includes three components:

- I. A Beacon network version 2 (objective 2 — based on individual beacons, objective 1);
- II. Query expansion services (objective 3);
- III. Data visualisation tools (objective 3).

All three are gathered under a single user interface (IV).

The Beacon network version 2 is a federated data discovery solution that comprehends Beacon v2 protocol providing an aggregation of results obtained from Beacons. It comprises an aggregator that serves to programmatically query the beacons that subscribed to the network, and gather all answers.

The query expansion (QE) services aim to improve the searchability and the interoperability of cohorts. Five type of expansion have been developed³:

1. Data driven expansion;
2. Ontological expansion;
3. Horizontal expansion — using the mapping between ontologies;
4. Vertical expansion — using the child/parent relation in ontologies;
5. Variant expansion.

To enhance the usability of the portal, the CRG used the principles developed in the horizontal query expansion⁴ — a service that retrieves synonyms based on semantic similarities, and adapted them to the Beacon model and terminologies. It is especially useful when trying to map terms that might be expressed differently across beacons.

Data visualisation tools aim to provide an overview of the available datasets in the federation, with breakdowns on some common phenotypic features such as biological sex, sample tissue type and disease. McGill has developed a prototype for some initial simple views on top of the analysis queries

² https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/new-release-of-ga4gh-beacon-expands-genomic-and-clinical-data-access/

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4609335>

⁴ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/query-expansion-horizontal-expansion>

⁵. The functions in the prototype were later used for the visualisations present in the portal (Figure 1, see also this [video](#)⁶ for a more specific example).

CINECA SYNTHETIC COHORT UK1

Figure 1. Initial cohort visualisation in the UI: distribution by sex and geographical origin.

The Federated discovery portal is a UI [<https://beacon-network-cineca-demo.ega-archive.org/>] that has been built at the CRG, on top of a Beacon network and adding QE as well as visualisation components.

The UI allows to query for individuals, that is, to search for study participants that fit certain criteria. Each beacon accepts a specific format for entries, so the “filtering terms” section helps identify which ontologies or terms that should be used in the query. The UI also offers an interactive way to modulate several parameters specifying the response (Figure 1). The “Resultset” parameter is set to `HIT` by default. Under this setting, results from the query will be returned. If the user wants to exclude the results from the query, they can set the Resultset parameter to `MISS`. The “Similarity” parameter allows modulating the response precision. Set to `HIGH`, it will strictly return results exactly similar to the query. However, if a user does not find enough results and want to include more terms that are related, though not identical, to the query, they can set the Similarity level to `LOW`. Finally, there is an option to include “Descendant terms” or not. If `TRUE` (the default setting), then it will include terms that belong to a given category (for example, “breast cancer” is one descendant of “cancer”).

⁵ <https://github.com/c3g/beacon-query-test>

⁶ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BxfSimp7al82CnQaV5ldG6aTm2szqZ7K/view>

Figure 2. The UI allows modulating the query response with ranges, Resultset, Similarity, Family tree. User interface screen capture.

An example of this type of query and response can be watched in the [individual query video](#)⁷. In it, the user first searches for ontology terms for “cardiomyopathy”, and then for the NCIT ontology for “female”. As the user is interested in individuals that weigh more than 85kg, they add a numerical query. The response shows 19 results, which can be detailed, since the dataset is synthetic and therefore not sensitive. The user finally filters⁸ the results to only select the individuals that also present sclerosis.

Horizontal QE allows the user to find equivalent terms (text-based) across different ontology systems. In the Portal, this service is accessible via the “query expansion button” on the main page. Once clicked, a new section appears: the user types the keyword they are looking for, and the ontologies they want to search it in. The response terms can then be submitted as filtering terms in order to specify a query. Those steps are exemplified in Figure 3 below:

⁷ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AigfM3kAAPJpJPRp63yzlvm3R1wsJQg/view>

⁸ note that there is also an option to order the results.

A The landing page shows a navigation bar with categories: INDIVIDUALS, BIOSAMPLES, VARIANT, RUNS, ANALYSES, COHORTS, CROSS QUERIES, NETWORK MEMBERS, and SIGN IN. A 'Query expansion' button is visible. Below it is a search bar with the placeholder text 'filtering term comma-separated, ID><=value'.

B The 'Horizontal query expansion' section shows a search for 'melanoma' and 'dhasdshd'. A red error message states: 'Not found. Please check the keyword and ontologies and retry'. Below is another search bar with the same placeholder text.

C The search results for 'melanoma' and 'ncit.mondo' are shown. The results are: 'Results found of exactly melanoma keyword from NCIT, MONDO ontologies: • NCIT:C3224 • MONDO:0005105'. There are 'RETURN' and 'SEARCH IN FILTERING TERMS' buttons.

D The search results are displayed as a list of filtering terms: 'NCIT:C3224'. Below the list is a search bar with the placeholder text 'filtering term comma-separated, ID><=value'.

E The search results are displayed as a list of filtering terms: 'NCIT:C3224'. Below the list is a search bar with the placeholder text 'filtering term comma-separated, ID><=value'. The results are: 'Results found of exactly melanoma keyword from NCIT, MONDO ontologies: • NCIT:C3224 • MONDO:0005105'. There is a 'New QE search' button.

At the bottom of the interface, there is a 'Granularity' section with options: [BOOLEAN](#), [COUNT](#), and [FULL RESPONSE](#). Below this, it shows '1 RESULT'.

Figure 3. Example of the integration of the horizontal query expansion (QE) service into the discovery portal. A: The QE button is visible on the landing page; B: An error message appears if the ontology is not found. C: The user lists the ontologies separated with a comma. D: The horizontal QE response, E: The responses can be used as a filtering term, here providing exactly one result.

User interface screen capture.

The Portal also includes a cohort section, which was a direct benefit of the work done in CINECA. It is possible to search for cohorts, select the ones to query, and use visualisation tools combined with filters. This [visualisation video](#)⁹ shows an example of what users can do. In this case, they are looking at disease distribution given a specific ethnicity.

The cross-query section allows for searching for specific individuals, biosamples, or variants, in specific data collections.

Finally, the Network members section shows which beacons are part of the network, their corresponding API, institution, and webpage.

3.3 Next steps

Now that a portal demo has been issued, the next steps will follow two main objectives: improve the user experience, and add more beacons to the network.

The network will be maintained by the CRG, and hosted at the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, with whom the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) has an agreement for permanent archiving of data and hosting of services. We will integrate the CINECA portal as a larger bioPortal for the EGA: the synthetic data will be discoverable for demonstration and training purposes, while sensitive data will be under controlled access only. Many beacons have already been implemented following the Beacon v2 specification (over a dozen in total, see CINECA deliverable D1.4 - Data interoperability documentation¹⁰, and four¹¹ in the context of CINECA, three of which have already joined the network), and more data providers are interested in *beaconising* their data. The CRG will provide appropriate support for these deployments to happen, and to help the network to grow.

The UI will be tested in real world situations during the summer of 2023. A user experience study will be performed in order to improve the UI, which should reach a stable version by the end of 2023. The EGA is planning to do an official launch to celebrate its finalisation.

⁹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BxfSimp7al82CnQaV5ldG6aTm2szqZ7K/view>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/record/8093973>

¹¹ EGA Beacon, CSC Finland Beacon, Bento Beacon in Quebec, and H3Africa Beacon

4. References

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5. Abbreviations

Centre for Genomic Regulation	CRG
European Genome-phenome Archive	EGA
Query expansion	QE
User interface	UI

6. Delivery and schedule

On time delivery.

7. Adjustments made

NA

